

An algebraic proof of Fermat's last theorem

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Abstract:

In 1995, A. Wiles announced, using cyclic groups, a proof of Fermat's Last Theorem, which is stated as follows: If π is an odd prime and x, y, z are relatively prime positive integers, then $z^\pi \neq x^\pi + y^\pi$. In this note, a proof of this theorem is offered, using elementary Algebra. It is proved that if π is an odd prime and x, y, z are positive integers satisfying $z^\pi = x^\pi + y^\pi$, then $x, y,$ and z are each divisible by π .

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The special case $z^4 = x^4 + y^4$ is impossible for relatively prime integers x, y, z [1]; it is only necessary to show that if $x, y, z,$ are relatively prime positive integers, π is an odd prime, $z^\pi \neq x^\pi + y^\pi$. If x and π are positive integers, the notation $x \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ will mean x is divisible by π . Let $C(\pi, k)$ represent the k^{th} coefficient of the binomial expansion of $(x + y)^\pi$; if π is prime, then $C(\pi, k) \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ for every $1 < k < \pi$.

Theorem 1. *If x, y, z are positive integers, π an odd prime and $x^\pi + y^\pi = z^\pi$, then $x \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}, y \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}, z \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$.*

Theorem 1 is arrived at as a result of two Lemmas.

Lemma 1. *If x, y, z are positive integers, π an odd prime, and $z^\pi = x^\pi + y^\pi$, then*

- (1) $(x + y)^\pi - z^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$;
- (2) $(z - x)^\pi - y^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$;
- (3) $(z - y)^\pi - x^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$;
- (4) $x + y - z \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$;
- (5) $(x + y)^\pi - z^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$;
- (6) $(z - x)^\pi - y^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$;
- (7) $(z - y)^\pi - x^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$;

$$(8) \quad x + y - z \neq 0.$$

Proof. Using the equation $z^\pi = x^\pi + y^\pi$, statements (1), (2), and (3) are obvious; (4), (5), (6), and (7) come from the equations

$$(eq.1) \quad (x + y)^\pi - z^\pi - (x + y - z)^\pi = \sum_1^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(x + y - z)^{\pi-k} z^k;$$

$$(eq.2) \quad (z - y)^\pi - x^\pi - (z - x - y)^\pi = \sum_1^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(z - x - y)^{\pi-k} x^k;$$

$$(eq.3) \quad (z - x)^\pi - y^\pi - (z - x - y)^\pi = \sum_1^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(z - x - y)^{\pi-k} y^k;$$

and the fundamental theorem of Arithmetic; (8) is obvious. leading to $xy = 0$.

Lemma 2. If π is an odd prime and x, y, z are positive integers such that $z^\pi = x^\pi + y^\pi$, then

$$(1) \quad xy \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

$$(2) \quad yz \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

$$(3) \quad xz \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$

Proof.

$$(x + y)^\pi - z^\pi = \sum_1^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}y^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2};$$

there is a k with $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}y^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$; order $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}y^k$ by inclusion and there exists k such that $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}y^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$;

$$(F1) \quad x^{\pi-k}y^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

multiplying by $x^k y^{\pi-k}$ gives $(xy)^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ which implies

$$(F1^*) \quad xy \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$

$$(z - y)^\pi - x^\pi = \sum_1^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(-1)^k y^{\pi-k} z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2};$$

there is a k with $C(\pi, k)y^{\pi-k}z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$; order $C(\pi, k)y^{\pi-k}z^k$ by inclusion and there exists k such that $C(\pi, k)y^{\pi-k}z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$;

$$(F2) \quad y^{\pi-k}z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

multiplying by $y^k z^{\pi-k}$ gives $(yz)^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ which implies

$$(F2^*) \quad yz \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$

$$(z - x)^\pi - y^\pi = \sum_1^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(-1)^k x^{\pi-k} z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2};$$

there is a k with $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$; order $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}z^k$ by inclusion and there exists k such that $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$;

$$(F3) \quad x^{\pi-k} z^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

multiplying by $x^k z^{\pi-k}$ gives $(xz)^\pi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ which implies

$$(F3^*) \quad xz \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$

The last three equivalences $(F1^*), (F2^*), (F3^*)$, along with $x + y - z \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ complete the proof.

Fermat's Last Theorem. If π is an odd prime and x, y, z are relatively prime positive integers, then $z^\pi \neq x^\pi + y^\pi$.

Proof. If π is an odd prime. then $z \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}; y \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}; x \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$.

References

- [1] H. Edwards, *Fermat's Last Theorem: A Genetic Introduction to Algebraic Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag, New York, (1977).
- [2] A. Wiles, *Modular elliptic curves and Fermat's Last Theorem*, Ann. Math. 141 (1995), 443-551.
- [3] A. Wiles and R. Taylor, *Ring-theoretic properties of certain Hecke algebras*, Ann. Math. 141 (1995), 553-573. *****Order $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}y^k$ by magnitude and there exists k such that $C(\pi, k)x^{\pi-k}y^k \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2}$ *****Wiles and R. Taylor, Ring-theoretic properties of certain Hecke algebras, Ann. Math. 141 (1995), 553-573. *****

$$(x + y)^\pi - z^\pi = \sum_0^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(x + y - z)^{\pi-k} z^k;$$

$$(x + y)^\pi - z^\pi = \sum_0^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(x + y - z)^{\pi-k} z^k;$$

$$(x + y - z)^\pi + \pi(x + y - z)z^{\pi-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2};$$

$$(x + y - z)^{\pi-2} + z^{\pi-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

$$z^{\pi-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

$$z \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$

$$(z-y)^\pi - x^\pi = \sum_0^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(z-x-y)^{\pi-k} x^k;$$

$$(z-x)^\pi - y^\pi = \sum_0^{\pi-1} C(\pi, k)(z-x-y)^{\pi-k} x^k;$$

$$(z-x-y)^\pi + \pi(z-x-y)x^{\pi-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi^2};$$

$$(z-x-y)^{\pi-2} + x^{\pi-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

$$x^{\pi-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi};$$

$$x \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$